

HYGROMECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CFRP UNDER CYCLIC HUMIDITY LOADINGS

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SUMMARY: Stable lightweight structures are key issues in the design and construction of the LHC high precision particle detectors. This paper presents the results of long term measurements performed on plates manufactured in Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP), material selected for these structures, subjected to cyclic humidity loadings. Test procedures are detailed; results on moisture absorption are described together with the related displacement measurements. These results indicate that cycling composites in the operating conditions of the LHC trackers does not provoke any major internal damage

KEYWORDS: dimensional stability, lightweight structures, moisture absorption, cyclic loading, CFRP

GENERAL

The LHC (Large Hadron Collider), one of the present "Big Science" projects, is a particle accelerator under construction at CERN. It is required by the High-Energy Particle Physics (HEP) community to look deeper into the structure of matter. The 7 TeV proton beams stored and accelerated to the speed of light by the accelerator will collide at the centre of huge detectors. The accelerator will be installed in a 27 km long tunnel, about 100 m underground. Its design is based on superconducting twin-aperture magnets, which operate in a superfluid helium bath at 1.9 K. The collisions between the protons will generate large amounts of sub-particles, signatures of new physics, which allows matter to be probed with a resolution of 10^{-19} meter. The detectors, installed around the collision points, have an overall cylindrical shape with both diameter and length up to 20 meters and weigh up to 15'000 tons. Trackers, the inner parts of these detectors, are designed to locate particles with a precision in the range of tens of microns within volumes of cubic meters. The detecting elements are intrinsically able to achieve this accuracy, but major errors could be caused by poor mechanical positioning and instability of the supporting structures.

STABLE STRUCTURES AND HUMIDITY

Design and construction of stable structures are key engineering problems for these HEP detectors with very stringent specifications [1]. The material choice is crucial: Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP), which combines lightweight and stiffness, has been preferred in most cases. Carbon-Carbon materials are also expected to be good candidates but the technological development is not far enough advanced to expect to build large reliable structures at an affordable cost.

The trackers are required to maintain their outstanding performance over a period of more than 10 years, withstanding somewhat harsh environmental conditions: ionising radiation, temperature and humidity cycles, etc. Environmental effects on CFRP are more or less known, but they clearly represent a drawback of plastics when compared with metallic structures. Radiation behaviour of materials has been thoroughly studied at CERN [2] and elsewhere. Temperature and temperature cycles on composites are quite well mastered and therefore taken into account when designing the structures. The low coefficient of thermal expansion of the carbon fibres is obviously an advantage. On the contrary, humidity and especially humidity cycles represent a field of research still to be fostered [3].

Coupling between these phenomena has also to be studied and could enhance the risk for the structures presently being designed.

Since the first measurements and theory dating back to the mid-seventies, knowledge of the mechanisms of moisture absorption and the related hygromechanical behaviour of composites has improved. Hundreds of articles have been published. However, when starting the design of the structures of the trackers, it was impossible to find reliable experimental information on the hygromechanical behaviour of CFRP under humidity cycles. In order to improve knowledge in this field and to create the necessary tools to design stable structures [4], a multi-year campaign of tests associated with a theoretical approach has been launched. Series of samples made in pure resins, unidirectional or multidirectional CFRP and Carbon-Carbon have been subjected to a series of humidity cycles simulating the environment expected inside the LHC detectors. The two types of resins selected for these tests are considered as the most commonly used by the Industry: the epoxy family is well-known for many years, well-mastered but absorbs significant quantities of humidity and the cyanate-ester family, newer on the market, more expensive but less hydrophilic.

This paper will only present results obtained on plates made in pure resins (epoxy and cyanate-ester) and unidirectional CFRP (T300/epoxy and T300/cyanate-ester). The results on the other samples will be published later.

HUMIDITY CYCLES ON CFRP PLATES

Test Procedure

Moisture absorption and desorption at room temperature are phenomena lasting typically over months for shell-like structures some millimetres thick. Acceleration of the tests can be achieved by increasing the test temperature; an Arrhenius-like law is fully applicable to diffusion phenomena. But the temperature increase should in any case be limited in order to minimise any potential chemical perturbations inside the resin; it is well-known that humidity absorption modifies the glass-transition temperature of the resins.

High precision and universal test set-ups have been developed by the Space industry to simulate the behaviour of environment sensitive "stable" structures. Inside this type of equipment, very accurate measurements, to better than a tenth of a micron, of the dimensions of samples and even of structures are possible under variable conditions (temperature, humidity). However, the very high operational cost of this equipment restricts their use over long periods and excluded its use to perform multi-year tests.

For these reasons, a specific test procedure based on more standard and cheaper equipment, a climatic chamber and a metrology equipment that can be found in any well-equipped workshop, has been developed.

The humidity cycling is performed in a standard climatic chamber, a KBF 720 APT Line from WTB Binder. Temperature regulation to within 0.4° C is quoted and the humidity is regulated to about 3 % RH. A double door equipped with plastic gloves has been added in order to allow manipulation of samples without perturbing the climatic conditions. A high precision balance has been added to the chamber to measure continuously the weight of the samples, up to 200 grams, and therefore their moisture intake. This balance, a METTLER PM200, has a reproducibility of 0.5 milligrams. It has been installed on a rigid support mechanically decoupled from the climatic chamber. A bar attached to the scale and going through a hole made at the top of the chamber is used to weigh the samples.

Deformations of the samples are measured on a metrology equipment Inspector Maxi 900 v from OLIVETTI OCN. A precision of the order of 3 microns is achieved on the measurements of the reference points. Samples are kept under conditions identical to those inside the climatic chamber by inserting them for a short period into a portable transparent climatic chamber especially designed for this purpose.

The apparatus and the procedure chosen do not lead to the highest precision but this can be improved by the use of large samples manufactured in a uniform fashion: relative errors on measurements are smaller and the edge effects could usually be neglected. Increasing the number of measured parts is also a way to improve the accuracy.

The test samples

Large thin plates have been chosen for the present measurements: their length and width are at least 250 mm and their thickness between 0.5 and 1.5 mm. Tables 1 and 2 give the dimensions and main characteristics of the samples considered here.

Table 1: The samples (resins and prepreps provided by CTMI (France))

Sample type	Material	Dimensions (mm)	Number of plates
Pure resin	Epoxy 1808N	250 x 250	3
Pure resin	Cyanate-Ester Rosalie	250 x 250	3
Unidirectional composite	T300/Epoxy 1808N	500 x 250	3
Unidirectional composite	T300/Cyanate-Ester Rosalie	500 x 250	3

Table 2: Measured thickness and fibre content of the plates

Plate reference	Average thickness	Fibre content (in weight)
Epoxy 1808N #1	1.12 mm	-
Epoxy 1808N #2	1.65 mm	-
Epoxy 1808N #3	1.19 mm	-
Cyanate-Ester #1	1.32 mm	-
Cyanate-Ester #2	1.48 mm	-
Cyanate-Ester #3	1.42 mm	-
T300/Epoxy 1808N #1	0.53 mm	55 %
T300/Epoxy 1808N #2	0.53 mm	56 %
T300/Epoxy 1808N #3	0.51 mm	58 %
T300/Cyanate-Ester #1	0.38 mm	71 %
T300/Cyanate-Ester #2	0.37 mm	71 %
T300/Cyanate-Ester #3	0.39 mm	71 %

Identical resins have been used for the manufacture of the pure resin and the unidirectional composite samples in order to allow comparison of results. The values given in Table 2 are average values: thickness has been measured on 24 points per plate and the fibre content has been determined by chemical attack and pyrolysis. Dispersions inherent to the size of the samples have to be kept in mind when analysing the results of the measurements.

Before polymerisation, small brass targets of a diameter of 0.2 mm have been inserted in the plates, 9 in the pure resin samples and 15 in the composite ones. Their relative positions are measured with the metrology equipment and allow differential displacements integrated over large lengths, and consequently the deformations, to be computed.

Humidity cycling

Under normal conditions, the trackers operate at room temperature or below. During the maintenance/assembly periods, the temperature may vary between 5° C and 25° C.

A stable temperature of 40° C has been chosen for the whole test campaign. This temperature, higher than the nominal one, leads to an enhancement of the diffusion inside the samples by a factor of at least 3. However, despite this acceleration, tests have been run over more than 2 years in order to get enough data to compare behaviour of the samples during subsequent cycles.

A change of the humidity from one level to the next was not usually made at saturation, which seems to be almost never reached in the range over which these tests have been performed, but largely after the abrupt change of slope of the weight-gain curve corresponding to a pseudo-saturation.

Humidity has been kept constant at the given level for periods lasting from 2.5 to 4 months. Taking into account the acceleration of the diffusion, this duration largely exceeds the 6 months expected operation cycle of the trackers.

First, the plates have been dried in vacuum in order to create well-defined initial conditions and then subjected to a series of successive humidity levels:

- first, in order to check the influence of the humidity on the moisture intake, the levels were maintained at 15 %, 35 %, 55 % and 85 %,
- then, cycling has been started, down to 15 % and up again, but only to 75 % in order to avoid condensation inside the climatic chamber, and followed by steps at 15 %, 75 % and finally 15 %.

Figure 1 shows the weight-gain curves plotted versus time for the six plates, both the pure resin ones and the composite ones, containing cyanate-ester. The reference weight of a plate in this Figure 1 is the weight measured immediately after removing the plates from vacuum. Similar curves have been obtained for the plates containing epoxy.

Figure 1: Weight-gain of plates containing cyanate-ester

Initial moisture intake

The influence of the humidity on the moisture intake of the plates during the first part of the campaign (0 to 85 %) has already been presented [5]. Moisture intake in epoxy and T300/epoxy plates can be modelled by a linear Fick's law with a fixed boundary concentration for low humidity levels (15 % and 35 %): after a linear increase of the moisture content corresponding to a flux proportional to the negative concentration gradient, a plateau is reached corresponding to a saturation level. But, the simple Fick's law is insufficient to describe all the other cases (larger humidity levels for epoxy-based plates and all cyanate-ester-based plates). The weight-gain data are then qualified as anomalous (pseudo-saturation). However, a two-phase model like Langmuir's law seems to be applicable in these latter cases.

Figure 2: Weight-gain versus (\sqrt{t} /thickness) for Epoxy 1808N plates

Figure 3: Weight-gain versus (\sqrt{t} /thickness) for T300/Epoxy 1808N plates

Figure 4: Weight-gain versus $(\sqrt{t}/\text{thickness})$ for Cyanate-Ester Rosalie plates

Figure 5: Weight-gain versus $(\sqrt{t}/\text{thickness})$ for T300/Cyanate-Ester Rosalie plates

Humidity cycling and moisture absorption

In order to take into account the influence of the thickness in the diffusion phenomena, all the weight-gain curves that follow will be plotted in the classical way, versus the square root of time divided by the thickness. The reference weight for a given humidity level will be the weight of the plate measured when this level is set to the new value.

Figures 2 to 5 give the plots obtained for all the plates for the absorption cycles between 15 % and 75 % and desorption cycles between 75 % and 15 %.

A qualitative examination of the initial part of all the curves does not show any noticeable difference between absorption and desorption and between the first cycle and the second one.

For both cycles, plates containing epoxy exhibit a Fickian behaviour in desorption with a very clear saturation level and a pseudo-Fickian behaviour in absorption. Saturation and pseudo-saturation levels are exactly proportional to the mass of resin for all the samples (except plate T300/Epoxy 1808N #3) but the second absorption cycle shows a slight increase of the composite plates absorption capability.

For both cycles, plates containing cyanate-ester desorb humidity down to a minimum value and then absorb it again. Their behaviour in absorption is more classically pseudo-Fickian. Saturation and pseudo-saturation levels are not exactly proportional to the mass of resin with a deficit for the composite plates, but the second absorption cycle shows an increase in their absorption capability.

Dimensional measurements

The positions of the targets on each plate have been measured at the beginning of the campaign and at the end of each humidity level. The longitudinal direction corresponds to the fiber orientation. Values of the transverse and longitudinal coefficients of moisture expansion (CME) can easily be obtained from these multi-point relative measurements. They are the expansional strain divided by the weight-gain expressed in %. However, problems on plates arose during the campaign: targets in some plates were found missing or upside-down (pre-curing problems) and pure resin plates started to bend due to relaxation of internal stresses over time. Moreover, difficulties maintaining environmental conditions have hampered the measurements. After a thorough analysis, it has been concluded that a measured CME smaller than 10^{-3} % H₂O was not meaningful.

As a result, only data on transverse CME are given for the composite plates. Table 3 gives the values of the CME measured during the humidity cycles.

Table 3: Coefficient of moisture expansion for the samples (average on 3 plates)

Samples	Humidity cycles			
	15 to 75 %	75 to 15 %	15 to 75 %	75 to 15 %
Epoxy 1808N	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Cyanate-Ester Rosalie	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
T300/Epoxy 1808N	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$
T300/Cyanate-Ester Rosalie	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$

A direct comparison of the hydromechanical behaviour of the composite plates under the same conditions can be made by checking the deformations at each cycle. Table 4 gives the transverse average deformation measured at each cycle. Note however that the thickness variations have not been taken into account.

Table 4: Transverse deformations of composite plates (average on 3 plates)

Samples	Humidity cycles			
	15 to 75 %	75 to 15 %	15 to 75 %	75 to 15 %
T300/Epoxy 1808N	$2.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-2.29 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.51 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-2.36 \cdot 10^{-3}$
T300/Cyanate-Ester Rosalie	$0.59 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-0.40 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$0.45 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-0.41 \cdot 10^{-3}$

These results confirm the superior performance of the cyanate-ester resin compared with the epoxy resin: a smaller coefficient of moisture expansion and a smaller moisture absorption. Based on Table 4, one can crudely say that a composite based on a cyanate-ester resin behaves 5 times better than a composite based on an epoxy resin. This difference is clearly large enough to compensate for abnormal behaviour of cyanate-ester in humidity cycling. In particular the moisture regain of cyanate-ester seen after a minimum in the desorption curve should not be forgotten since this occurs when the trackers are in operation and therefore when they must be stable and in a dry environment.

CONCLUSION

Hundreds of measurements have been performed on the composite plates quoted in this paper but also on other composite plates. Much more information could be extracted from this campaign. This could be the basis for more accurate computations of the behaviour of CFRP under humidity cycles.

Despite the relatively low capital investment, results are accurate enough to be useful. It is confirmed that cyanate-ester has a lower moisture absorption and a moisture expansion than epoxy. This advantage is kept in cycling conditions despite some slight anomalous effects.

These results indicate that cycling composites in the operating conditions of the LHC trackers does not provoke any major internal damage and, therefore, no serious degradation of the mechanical properties could be feared.

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REFERENCES

1. C. Hauviller, "High Performance Composite Structures for High Precision Particle Detectors", *11th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Gold Coast (Australia), July 1997
2. M. Tavlet et al, "Compilation of Radiation Damage Test Data, Part II, 2nd edition: Thermoset and thermoplastics resins, composite materials", *CERN 98-01* (1998)
3. P. Kanoute et al., "Hygrothermal Behaviour of Fibre Reinforced Composite Materials", *Seventh International Conference on Fibre Reinforced Composites*, Newcastle (United Kingdom), April 1998
4. S. Da Mota Silva et al, "Hygro-Thermal Transient Analysis For Highly Stable Structures", *12th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Paris (France), July 1999
5. P. Kanoute, "Etude du Comportement Hygromécanique de Matériaux Composites à Matrice Polymérique", *Doctoral thesis*, University Paris VI (France), March 1999.